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InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy

D7.1 DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan

Summary

The InBestSoil communication, dissemination and exploitation plan focuses on efficient knowledge transfer through dissemination activities, multi-channel communication, participation in events, creation of dissemination and training materials, and development of a long-term exploitation and sustainability strategy. Annexes I, II, III, and IV provide detailed information on the plan's components, dissemination/communication tasks and content types, key performance indicators, exploitable results, and associated protection mechanisms. Regular updates and ongoing adjustments ensure the plan remains dynamic and responsive to project progress.

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JUNE	Iuliana Floricica [JUNE] Bianca Caragea [JUNE] Ina Stoica [JUNE] Elena Zamfirescu [JUNE] Adelina Manea [JUNE] Diego Soto Gómez [UVigo]		
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	E	Ethics	
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	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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1. Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan of InBestSoil is an essential component to ensure the effective dissemination of project results to diverse audiences and maximize their impact. Throughout different stages and timelines, a series of activities and strategic actions have been identified to achieve this objective. All actions considered here are in line with that stated in the Description of Action.

First, the importance of internal and external communication from the beginning of the project is highlighted. In month 3, the launch of the project has been carried out with a press release addressed to the general public, potential partners and stakeholders. This has been done through corporate communication channels, such as sustainability media, agriculture, business and general media. In addition, InBestSoil's social media channels have been used to reach a wider audience.

In month 5, we plan to launch the InBestSoil website, which will be an important reference point for information about the project. This allows reaching the general public, potential partners and stakeholders through marketing channels, both on the InBestSoil website itself and on InBestSoil's social networks. At the same time, a branding guide will be developed for WP leaders, which will include guidelines and visual identity elements for consistent communication.

As the project progresses, general communications and updates on project objectives and progress will be made. These communications will be targeted to the general public, potential partners and stakeholders through infographics and media interviews. In addition, video campaigns are planned for both the Living Labs (LHs & LLs) and the overall project, which will be shared on social media and the website.

In month 9, an online banner campaign will be conducted targeting the general public, potential partners and stakeholders. These visual banners will be displayed on the consortium partners' websites, social media and the project website. In month 10, further media interviews are planned to share project objectives and updates with the business community and specialized media.

Throughout the project, regular updates will also be made to keep stakeholders informed. These updates will be in the form of infographics and will be shared on social media and the project website. In addition, sets of practice abstracts are planned, which will be brochures targeted to potential partners and stakeholders. These brochures will be distributed through the project website and digital platform.

In month 48, a final international conference will be held in Brussels to disseminate the project results. This event will be attended by the scientific community, policymakers, NGOs, farmers, industry, and other relevant stakeholders. Face-to-face presentations and discussions will be held at this event to share results and foster collaboration.

In addition to communication activities, the exploitation plan focuses on the long-term sustainability of the project results and their practical application. Different tools and resources are being developed, such as a collaborative platform for stakeholders to share results and publications beyond the project, a soil health

indicator kit and total economic value of soil health, an online calculator for the economic value of soil ecosystem services, and prototypes of digital systems for redesigning farms towards regenerative agriculture. These tools will be available to stakeholders under open licenses and will be promoted through online platforms and repositories.

All this information is included in Annex I.

On the other hand, Annex II includes the tasks and types of content related to the dissemination plan, including interviews, opinion articles, press releases and content for blogs, media articles and specialized articles. These tasks will address different aspects related to:

- Understanding and addressing the impact of climate change on soil characteristics and health. This includes studying the impact of climate change on different soil types, soil degradation due to agricultural practices, and the need to adopt sustainable agricultural practices to slow climate change and increase soil fertility.
- Promote sustainable agriculture that does not harm the environment and is aligned with European policies. Agricultural practices that not only protect soil health, but also biodiversity and ecological balance will be discussed.
- Living Labs and their impact on the soil. Living Labs are experimental and learning spaces for the development and implementation of practices related to improving soil health. Aspects such as the methodology for developing Living Labs, the establishment of Living Labs and their effects on the surrounding environment, as well as the evaluation of the long-term impacts of soil interventions will be explored.
- Economic value of ecosystem services provided by healthy soils. This involves assessing the economic value of environmental and social benefits derived from soil conservation and improvement, which can be relevant to support decisions and policymaking.
- Integration of soil health into business models. That is, understanding how sustainable agricultural practices and soil conservation can generate economic benefits and be an integral part of agricultural business models.

The channels to be used in the dissemination plan include media related to sustainability, agriculture and business, as well as scientific journals specialized in environmental and soil issues. InBestSoil's social media will also be used to disseminate information and keep in touch with the audience.

Annex III includes the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that the communication and dissemination activities are intended to achieve. The evaluation of these KPIs will be used to review the effectiveness of the planned dissemination and communication activities.

Finally, in Annex IV, the exploitable results, the exploitation strategy associated and the protection mechanism.

In conclusion, the InBestSoil communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan encompasses a wide range of strategic activities and planned actions to ensure effective knowledge transfer and maximize project impact. Through various communication strategies, participation in external events, seminars and

conferences, and the creation of tools and resources for long-term sustainability, InBestSoil aims to disseminate its results and promote the adoption of soil-healthy practices in various sectors and audiences. It is important to mention that this plan and its annexes will be updated with new activities as the project progresses, and there is an update planned for month 48 (D7.6 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan Update).

Annex I – InBestSoil: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

Month (deadline)	Category	Topics	Target Audience	Content	Channels	Recurrence	Responsible
M3	C	Project Kick Off	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Press Release	Sustainability, Business, General, Agriculture Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE, WP leaders
M5	C	Website Launch	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Website	Owned - website, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE
M5	C	Brand Book	WP leaders	Branding Guide & stationery	Internal	1	JUNE
M5	C	General Comms	WP leaders	Plan	Internal	1	JUNE
M6	C, D & E	Platform Launch	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Digital Platform	InBestSoil Platform	1	LGI
M6	C	Project Goals	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Media Interview	Sustainability, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE
M6	C	Project Updates 1	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WPs

M6	C	Video Campaign - LHs & LLs	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Video	Social Media, Website	9	JUNE, LHs & LLs coordinators
M9	C	Online Banner Campaign	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Visual	Consortium Partners Website, Social Media, Project's Website	1	All
M10	C	Project Goals & Updates	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Media Interview	Sustainability, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE
M12	C	Project Updates 2	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WPs
M15	C	Project Evolution	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Press Release	Sustainability, Business, General, Agriculture Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE, WP leaders
M18	C	Project Updates 3	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WPs
M18	C	Project Updates	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Media Interview	Sustainability, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE
M24	C	Project Updates 4	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WP

M24	C	Project Updates - 2 years	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Media Interview	Sustainability, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE
M24	C	Practice Abstracts - Batch 1	Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Leaflets	Website, Digital Platform	50	All WPs
M24	C	Video Campaign - general project videos	Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Video	Social Media, Website	2	All WPs
M26	C	Project Brochures	Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Leaflets	Website, Digital Platform	2	All WPs
M30	C	Project Evolution	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Press Release	Sustainability, Business, General, Agriculture Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE, WP leaders
M30	C	Project Updates 5	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WPs
M31	C	Project Evolution & next steps	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Media Interview	Sustainability, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE, WP leaders
M36	C	Project Updates 6	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WPs
M36	C	Online Banner Campaign	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Visual	Consortium Partners Website, Social Media, Project's Website	1	All WPs

M42	C	Project Updates 7	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WPs
M42	C	Leaflet with key messages for LHs / LLs for business innovation related to soil health	Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Leaflets	Website, Social Media, Digital Platform	9	All WPs
M48	C	Project Final	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Press Release	Sustainability, Business, General, Agriculture Media, InBestSoil Social Media	1	JUNE, WP leaders
M48	C	Project Final	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Media Interview	Sustainability, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media	3	JUNE, WP leaders
M48	C	Project Updates 8	General Public, Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Infographic	Social Media, Website	1	All WPs
M48	C	Practice Abstracts - Batch 2	Potential Partners, Stakeholders	Leaflets	Website, Digital Platform	50	All WPs
M48	C	End of project report	WP leaders, Potential Partners, Stakeholders, EU Commission	Report	Internal, External - Commission Reporting	1	All WPs

Ongoing	D	Participation in external events, such as fairs, conferences, and congresses, where results will be show-cased (posters, presentations, etc.)	Scientific community, farmers, foresters, miners, public authorities, industry, businesses, investors, land managers, policymakers	Events	Live face to face event, social media comms, general public PR	6 international events, 20 national/regional events	INX, All WPs
Starting from M16	D	Field demonstration events; 2 events per LH/ LL showing the benefits of preserving soil health	The scientific community, policymakers, NGOs, farmers/ forest/ miners, industry, land managers, public authorities, businesses, investors, civil society	Demonstration	Live face to face event, social media comms, scientific publications, general public PR	18	INX, LH and LL coordinators Partners
Starting from M14	D	InBestSoil workshops/seminars/webinars, in the framework of the stakeholder platforms to present main results	Scientific community, policy makers, farmers/foresters, miners/ public authorities, industry, businesses, investors, land managers, civil society	Workshops/ Seminars / Webinars	Online or live face to face event, social media comms, general public PR	18	INX, LH and LL coordinators, ZABA

Starting from M15	D	University lectures to explain the recent project results and help up skill the next generation of students in investing in soil health	500 Bachelor, PhD and Master Students	University Lectures	Live face to face lectures	10	INX, LH and LL coordinators, ZABA
M48	D	Final International Conference in Brussels to disseminate results	The scientific community, policymakers, NGOs, farmers/ forest/ miners, industry, land managers, public authorities, businesses, investors, and civil society; 200 attendees	Conference	Live face to face presentation & discussions	1	INX
M48	D	Training and Dissemination materials: Partners will explain the project and project results to various audiences through dedicated platforms and popular articles published in national and international sectorial magazines	Farmers/foresters/miners, industry, businesses, investors, land managers, public authorities, NGOs, civil society	Practice Abstracts, Factsheets, Videos, Articles	Practice Abstracts (EIP-AGRI) and associated factsheets, practice oriented short videos and podcasts, infographics, articles in sector-specific magazines	100 Practice Abstracts, 9 infographics, 9 videos, 9 podcasts, 20 articles	JUNE, INX, UVIGO, LH and LL coordinators

Starting from M13	D	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed JCR journals under open-access	Scientific community	Scientific Articles	Scientific Magazines	20	INX, LH and LL coordinators
M48	D	Policy Brief, as recommendations for policymakers to influence future policy and regulatory actions. These will be presented at the Final Conference	Policymakers, public authorities	Policy brief	EU portal	1	CMCC
M48	E	Long-term sustainability plan	Potential Partners, Stakeholders, EU Commission	Plan	Internal, External - Commission Reporting	1	All WPs
M5	E	LL and LH collaborative platform. Enables stakeholders to share results and publications on the platform beyond the project	Farmers/foresters/miners, industry, businesses, investors, land managers, public authorities, NGOs	Platform	Online platform	1	LGI

M8	E	Toolkit of soil health indicators and total economic value of soil health. Open license for end-users to apply the knowledge	Farmers/foresters/miners, industry, businesses, investors, land managers	Indicators toolkit	Open license for end users	1	UPCT
M40	E	Web-based calculator for the economic value of soil ecosystem services.	Farmers/foresters/miners, industry, businesses, investors, land managers	Web based calculator	Utility model for end users	1	UPCT
M26	E	Prototypes of digital system applications for land managers to redesign farms for a transition to regenerative agriculture	Farmers/foresters/miners, land managers	Digital systems prototypes (Business Model Canvas)	License	1	WU/ UOE

M12	E	Policy conditions and catalogs of existing soil health economic and policy incentives. Science-policy events (e.g., EU Green Week and/or Conference on modeling for policy support)	Farmers/foresters/miners, industry, businesses, investors, land managers, public authorities, NGOs	Catalogs and scientific documentation	Events / Seminars / Workshops	TBD	CMCC
M35	E	Toolbox of incentive schemes for soil health. Distributed via repositories (e.g., OPPLA, Knowledge4Policy)	Farmers/foresters/miners, industry, land managers	Digital assets	Open-access database	1	CMCC
M48	E	Report on Policy recommendations for soil health protection.	Farmers/foresters/miners, industry, businesses, investors, land managers, public authorities, NGOs	Scientific Articles	Report and open access scientific publications	1	CMCC

C, communication; D, dissemination; E, exploitation; TBD, to be decided; WP, work package; LH, lighthouse; and LL, living lab.

Annex II –Communication and Dissemination: Interviews, Articles and other scheduled elements

Topics	Details	Content Type	Channels
The impact of climate change on soil characteristics	Interview with somebody from University of Cartagena	Interview	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
Sustainable agriculture: low costs, without harming the environment & alignment with European policies	Interview with Diego Soto Gomez	Interview	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
Soil degradation through agricultural works. How deep farming tools can be replaced?	Insights from Zagreb University	Opinion Article	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
Biodiversity and increasing soil fertility - What practices farmers need to adopt to stop climate change?	Insights from FiBL (Research Institute for Organic Agriculture, Switzerland)	Opinion Article	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
The impact of climate change on different soil types	An extensive study to discuss the different types of soil, their particularities and the impact of climate change on them.	Press Release, Blog Content	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
The boreal forest, a way to store carbon	Article on how this type of forest, and therefore soil, helps store carbon. Although boreal forests only cover about 11% of the earth's land surface, they store one third of the world's terrestrial carbon stocks.	Media Article, Content Pitching Blog	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media

Technosols - What they are and why they should be used?	Defining the concept, explaining it and how it can contribute to the restoration of contaminated soils	Media Article, Content	Pitching Blog	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
Intensive agriculture: What effects it has on the soil?	Educational article	Media Article, Content	Pitching Blog	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
What are the needs of the project stakeholders?	Interviews with partners participating in LLs and LHs.	Media Article, Content	Pitching Blog	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
The circular economy and its impact on agriculture	Interviews with partners dealing with research in LL and LH	Media Article, Content	Pitching Blog	Sustainability, Agriculture, Business Media, InBestSoil Social Media
Methods and methodology to develop Living Labs	Exploring the approaches and methodologies for establishing and operating Living Labs. The research explores the process and approaches for establishing Living Labs within the context of the InBestSoil project. Living Labs are collaborative research and innovation platforms that involve multiple stakeholders, including researchers, practitioners, policymakers, and citizens, to co-create and test solutions in real-world settings. The publication aims to provide insights into the methods and methodology employed by the InBestSoil project to develop and implement Living Labs focused on soil health. It explores the participatory and interdisciplinary approaches used to engage stakeholders and facilitate knowledge exchange and co-design processes.	Scientific Article		Journal of Environmental Management

Experiences from Setting up a Living Lab: Effects on the Surrounding Environment	Sharing lessons learned and experiences from establishing a Living Lab. Focuses on sharing the lessons learned and experiences gained from establishing a Living Lab within the framework of the InBestSoil project, specifically regarding contamination issues and their potential impacts on the surrounding environment. The publication delves into the challenges and considerations associated with setting up a Living Lab that involves interventions or experiments related to soil health. It explores the potential for contaminations, such as the use of fertilizers, pesticides, or soil amendments, and the measures taken to mitigate their adverse effects on the environment.	Scientific Article	Environmental Pollution
Life Cycle Inventory and Development of Living Labs	Assessing the environmental impacts and conducting life cycle assessments for the development of Living Labs. Explores the integration of life cycle inventory (LCI) methodologies in the development and operation of Living Labs within the InBestSoil project. LCI is a systematic approach used to quantify and assess the environmental impacts associated with a product, process, or system throughout its entire life cycle. The publication focuses on how LCI methodologies are applied to assess the environmental footprint of interventions and activities conducted within the Living Labs of the InBestSoil project. It examines the data collection, analysis, and interpretation processes involved in developing comprehensive life cycle inventories for the different interventions related to soil health.	Scientific Article	Science of the Total Environment

<p>Life Cycle and CO2 Production of the Creation of a Living Lab within the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Investigating the carbon footprint and environmental impacts associated with establishing a Living Lab. Focuses on assessing the life cycle and carbon dioxide (CO2) emissions associated with the establishment and development of a Living Lab within the context of the InBestSoil project. The publication aims to quantify and evaluate the environmental impacts and carbon footprint of the activities involved in creating a Living Lab. The study explores the different stages of creating a Living Lab, including site preparation, infrastructure development, equipment installation, and ongoing operational activities. It examines the energy consumption, material inputs, and associated CO2 emissions throughout the life cycle of the Living Lab.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Heliyon</p>
<p>Differences on Soil Effects of a Living Lab and Surrounding Areas within the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Comparing soil properties, nutrient content, and overall soil health between a Living Lab and its surrounding areas. Investigates and compare the soil effects and characteristics within a Living Lab and its surrounding areas in the context of the InBestSoil project. The publication aims to understand and analyze the potential differences in soil properties, nutrient content, microbial diversity, and overall soil health between the controlled environment of the Living Lab and the adjacent natural or agricultural landscapes. The study utilizes field sampling and laboratory analysis to collect soil samples from both the Living Lab and the surrounding areas. It examines various soil parameters, such as pH, organic matter content, nutrient levels, soil structure, and microbial community composition, to assess the differences between the two environments.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Applied Soil Ecology</p>

<p>Community Effects of a Soil Control Lighthouse in Relation to the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Examining the impacts of a LH on the surrounding community and community engagement. Examines the impacts and benefits of a LH on the surrounding community within the framework of the InBestSoil project. A LH is a demonstration site or facility that showcases innovative soil management practices and serves as an educational resource for the local community. The publication focuses on evaluating the community effects resulting from the establishment and operation of a LH. It explores the engagement and participation of community members in the activities and knowledge sharing initiatives offered by the LH. It assesses the extent to which the LH contributes to community empowerment, awareness, and capacity building in soil health management.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety</p>
<p>Past, Present, and Future of Mission Soil: Effects on the Environment and Society within the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Analyzing the historical, current, and future perspectives of Mission Soil and its impacts on the environment and society. Delves into the historical, current, and future perspectives of Mission Soil and its impact on the environment and society. Mission Soil refers to the overarching goals and objectives of the InBestSoil project in promoting sustainable soil management practices. The publication provides an overview of the historical context of soil management practices and the challenges and impacts associated with unsustainable soil practices in the past. It highlights the need for transformative actions and the InBestSoil project's mission to address soil degradation, soil erosion, and other negative effects on the environment and society.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Environmental Research</p>

<p>Economic Valuation of Ecosystem Services Provided by Healthy Soils: A Case Study of the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Explore the economic value of ecosystem services provided by healthy soils, using the InBestSoil project as a case study. The publication will explore the economic value of the ecosystem services delivered by healthy soils, using the InBestSoil project as a case study to demonstrate the methodology and findings developed on the project. In addition, the publication will explore the benefits of developing projects to take care of the soil health.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Chemosphere</p>
<p>Assessing the Long-Term Impacts of Soil Interventions on Ecosystem Resilience: Insights from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Examine the long-term effects of soil interventions on ecosystem resilience, drawing insights from the InBestSoil project. The publication investigates the lasting effects of soil interventions on ecosystem resilience, using insights from the InBestSoil Project. It analyses various interventions, their influence on soil health, and their contributions to long-term ecosystem stability. The study enhances understanding of soil management practices for resilient and sustainable ecosystems.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry</p>
<p>Incorporating Soil Health into Business Models: Lessons from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Explore how businesses can integrate soil health considerations into their models, using the InBestSoil project as an example. The publication explores the integration of soil health considerations into business models, drawing valuable lessons from the InBestSoil Project. The publication examines how businesses can incorporate soil health as a strategic element in their operations and decision-making processes. The study investigates successful examples and best practices from the project, in a way to highlight how businesses have embraced soil health as a key component of their model.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Environmental Pollution</p>
<p>Public-Private Partnerships for Investing in Soil Health: Experiences from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Analyze the experiences and outcomes of public-private partnerships in investing in soil health, using the InBestSoil project as a case study. The experiences and outcomes of public-private partnerships in the context of investing on soil health, drawing insight from the project is the main topic of</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Utilities Policy</p>

	<p>the publication. It will explore the collaborative efforts between public and private organizations to promote and support initiatives aimed at improving soil health. The study examines the specific partnerships established within the project, involving diverse stakeholders. It analyses the roles, responsibilities, and contributions of each partner in advancing soil health objectives, including financial investments, knowledge sharing and implementation of sustainable practices.</p>		
<p>Evaluating the Role of Agricultural Practices in Soil Degradation: Insights from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Examine the impact of agricultural practices on soil degradation, drawing on research from the InBestSoil project. The focus of the publication will be on the assessment of agricultural practices and their impact on soil degradation, utilizing valuable insights derived from the InBestSoil project. The publication will try to deepen the understanding of the relationship between agricultural activities and soil degradation processes. For that, comprehensive research and analysis conducted within the project, the publication investigates various agricultural practices, including tillage methods, irrigation techniques, fertilizer application, and crop rotation systems. It will try to examine how these practices influence soil degradation processes such as erosion, nutrient depletion, compaction, and loss of organic matter.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Soil and Tillage Research</p>
<p>Quantifying the Economic Benefits of Soil Conservation Practices: Lessons Learned from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Quantify the economic benefits of soil conservation practices, sharing insights from the InBestSoil project. This publication would quantify the economic benefits of soil conservation practices and share lessons learned from the InBestSoil project's investigations. The research focuses on the quantification of economic benefits associated with soil conservation practices, drawing valuable lessons from the project. The publication aims to provide insights into the financial implications of implementing soil conservation practices and their contribution to sustainable land management.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>International Soil and Water Conservation Research</p>

<p>Analyzing the Socioeconomic Impacts of Soil Degradation: Evidence from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Analyze the socioeconomic consequences of soil degradation, using evidence from the InBestSoil project. This publication would analyze the socioeconomic consequences of soil degradation, using evidence and research outcomes from the InBestSoil project. For that, it focuses on the assessment of the socioeconomic consequences of soil degradation, drawing upon evidence and findings from the InBestSoil Project. The publication aims to shed light on the multifaceted impacts of soil degradation on society, the economy, and human well-being.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>International Soil and Water Conservation Research</p>
<p>Designing Effective Policy Instruments to Promote Investment in Soil Health: Lessons from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Explore the design of policy instruments to incentivize investment in soil health, using the InBestSoil project as a source of lessons. This publication would provide insights into designing policy instruments that effectively incentivize investment in soil health, drawing lessons and recommendations from the InBestSoil project. The publication wants to explore the development of policy instruments that effectively incentivize and promote investment in soil health, drawing upon valuable lessons learned from the InBestSoil Project. The publication aims to provide insights into the design and implementation of policies that encourage sustainable soil management practices.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Utilities Policy</p>

<p>The Role of Stakeholder Engagement in Promoting Soil Health: Experiences from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Explore the importance of stakeholder engagement in promoting soil health initiatives, drawing on experiences from the InBestSoil project. This publication would explore the importance of stakeholder engagement in promoting soil health initiatives and sharing experiences and best practices from the InBestSoil project. For that, it delves into the significance of stakeholder engagement in advancing soil health initiatives, based on valuable experiences and insights derived from the InBestSoil Project. The publication focuses on the collaborative efforts and active participation of diverse stakeholders in promoting and implementing practices that enhance soil health.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Applied Soil Ecology</p>
<p>Assessing the Cost-Effectiveness of Soil Interventions: Insights from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Assess the cost-effectiveness of soil interventions, providing insights from the InBestSoil project. This publication would assess the cost-effectiveness of different soil interventions, offering insights and findings from the InBestSoil project's research. The research researches the evaluation of the cost-effectiveness of soil interventions, drawing valuable insights from the InBestSoil Project. The publication aims to provide evidence-based assessments of the economic efficiency and viability of different soil interventions in improving soil health and ecosystem sustainability.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Annals of Agricultural Sciences</p>

<p>Integrating Soil Health Indicators into Environmental Management Systems: Lessons from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Discuss the integration of soil health indicators into environmental management systems, using the InBestSoil project as an example. This publication would discuss the integration of soil health indicators into environmental management systems, using the InBestSoil project as a source of lessons and examples. The study examines the selection, development, and implementation of soil health indicators within the context of environmental management systems. It explores how indicators related to soil fertility, organic matter content, soil structure, biodiversity, and nutrient cycling can be effectively integrated into monitoring protocols and reporting mechanisms.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Journal of Environmental Management</p>
<p>Exploring the Potential of Digital Technologies in Monitoring Soil Health: Case Studies from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>Explore the use of digital technologies for monitoring soil health, presenting case studies from the InBestSoil project. This publication would explore the use of digital technologies for monitoring soil health, presenting case studies and outcomes from the InBestSoil project's exploration of this area. The research explores various digital technologies employed within the InBestSoil Project, such as remote sensing, geographic information systems (GIS), sensor networks, and data analytics. It showcases how these technologies enable real-time and spatially explicit monitoring of soil health parameters, providing researchers and land managers with valuable information for decision-making and adaptive management practices</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Computers and Electronics in Agriculture</p>

<p>Quantifying the Carbon Sequestration Potential of Healthy Soils: Lessons Learned from the InBestSoil Project</p>	<p>This publication would quantify the carbon sequestration potential of healthy soils, drawing on lessons learned from the InBestSoil project's research and investigations. The publication aims to enhance our understanding of the role of soil health in carbon storage and its implications for climate change mitigation. Through comprehensive research and analysis conducted within the InBestSoil Project, the publication examines the relationship between soil health indicators and carbon sequestration. It explores how healthy soils, characterized by high organic matter content, improved soil structure, and enhanced microbial activity, can contribute to the long-term storage of carbon in the form of soil organic carbon.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Science of the Total Environment</p>
<p>Assessing the Impacts of Climate Change on Crop Yields and Food Security</p>	<p>Assess the impacts of climate change on crop yields and food security, considering the role of soil health in mitigating these effects. This publication would assess the impacts of climate change on crop yields and food security, considering the role of soil health in mitigating these effects. The study incorporates various modelling approaches, statistical analyses, and scenario simulations to project the potential future impacts of climate change on crop yields. It examines the interactions between climate variables, such as temperature, rainfall, and CO2 concentrations, and their influence on crop growth, phenology, and nutrient uptake.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Advances in Climate Change Research</p>

<p>Investigating the Effects of Urban Green Spaces on Mental Health and Well-being</p>	<p>This publication would investigate the effects of urban green spaces on mental health and well-being, examining the contribution of soil health in these spaces. The publication aims to deepen our understanding of the relationship between access to green spaces in urban environments and the psychological benefits they provide. Through comprehensive research and analysis, the publication investigates the positive effects of urban green spaces on mental health. It examines how exposure to nature, such as parks, gardens, and urban forests, can enhance psychological well-being, reduce stress levels, and improve overall mental health outcomes.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Urban Climate</p>
<p>Assessing the Impacts of Climate Change on Forest Ecosystem Dynamics</p>	<p>This publication would assess the impacts of climate change on forest ecosystem dynamics, considering the role of soil health in maintaining the resilience of these ecosystems. The publication aims to deepen our understanding of how climate change influences various aspects of forest ecosystems, including species composition, carbon sequestration, nutrient cycling, and overall ecosystem health.</p>	<p>Scientific Article</p>	<p>Forest Ecology and Management</p>

Annex III – InBestSoil: Communication and Dissemination activities/tools with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Category	Activities / Tools	KPIs
Dissemination	Participation in external events, such as fairs, conferences, congresses, where results will be show-cased (posters, presentations, etc.)	> 6 international events
		> 20 national/regional events
		> 10,000 people reached (audience)
Dissemination	InBestSoil workshops/seminars/webinars, in the framework of the stakeholder platforms to present main results	> 2 events per LH/LL
		> 1000 people (attendees)
Dissemination	Field demonstration events organized in each LH to show benefits of preserving soil health	> 2 events per LH
		> 500 people (attendees)
Dissemination	University lectures to explain the recent project results and help up skill the next generation of students in investing in soil health	> 500 Bachelor, Master and PhD students addressed
Dissemination	Final International Conference in Brussels to disseminate results	> 200 attendees
Dissemination	Training and Dissemination materials: Partners will explain the project and project results to various audiences through dedicated platforms and popular articles published in national and international sectorial magazines	More than: 100 Practice Abstracts (EIP-AGRI) and associated factsheets, 9 practice oriented short videos (tutorials), 9 practice-oriented podcasts, 9 practice-oriented Infographics and 20 articles in sector-specific magazines
Dissemination	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed JCR journals under open-access	> 20 articles
Dissemination	Policy brief, as recommendations for policymakers to influence future policy and regulatory actions. These will be presented at the Final Conference	At least one policy brief
Communication		> 30,000 visits

	Website. A user-friendly website will be established as the main information hub for the project	> 70 items accumulated
Communication	Social Media. InBestSoil specific social networks profiles (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, YouTube) will be set-up in English and national languages.	> 1000 followers in social media
		> 10,000 interactions
		> 2500 YouTube visualizations
		> 3 key opinion leaders (KOLs) engaged
Communication	Audio-visual Materials. JUNE will design communication materials that will be centralized in a branding guideline document and updated regularly to adapt to different messages communicated.	2 general leaflets/brochures
		4 general infographics
		2 promotional videos
		9 short videos (> 2500 views)
Communication	Online Banners to present the concept of InBestSoil, following branding rules, in different formats for communication media, websites, social media, etc.	2 campaigns
Communication	Press Releases will emphasize the InBestSoil vision and key results. An international database of journalists will be built. The Communication Manager will organize interviews with journalists to present project objectives and progress.	> 20 interviews
		> 1000 media clippings
Communication	Partners' Channels. Access to partners existing communication channels such as their websites, social networks accounts, etc.	> 10.000 people as a potential audience to be reached

Annex IV – InBestSoil Key exploitable results, exploitation strategy associated and protection mechanisms

Partner	Key Result (KER)	Exploitable	Exploitation strategy / Exploitation path	Protection mechanism
LGI	LL and LH collaborative platform		Enable stakeholders to share results and publications on the platform beyond the project	/
UPCT	Toolkit of soil health indicators and total economic value of soil health		Open license for end-users to apply the knowledge to assess soil health indicators to further give them a monetary value	CC-BY license
UPCT	Web-based calculator for the economic value of soil ecosystem services		Utility model for end-users to apply the process to give a monetary value to their soils	Utility model
WU/UEO	Prototypes of digital system applications for land managers to redesign farms for a transition to regenerative agriculture		License/Further research needed	/
CMCC	Policy conditions and catalogues of existing soil health economic and policy incentives		Science-policy events (e.g. EU Green Week and/or Conference on modelling for policy support)	Report and open access scientific publication
CMCC	Toolbox of incentive schemes for soil health		Distributed via repositories (e.g., OPPLA , Knowledge4Policy)	Open access database
CMCC	Report on Policy recommendations for soil health protection.		Distributed standalone and as a part of European assessment reports such as by EFDRR , EEA...	Report and open access scientific publication

